

The Influence of Project Communication Planning Skills in Implementation of Water Projects in Kenya

Emmanuel Kipkorir Cherop¹, Dr. Fridah Simba^{*2}, Dr. Muchelule Yusuf Wanjala ^{*3}

¹Doctoral Candidate; Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology;
P.O. Box 62000-00200 Nairobi, Kenya.

²Senior Lecturer; Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology,
P.O. Box 62000-00200 Nairobi, Kenya.

³Senior Lecturer; Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology,
P.O. Box 62000-00200 Nairobi, Kenya.

Abstract: This study is to determine the influence of communication planning Skills on implementation of water projects in Kenya. Communication accommodation theory was referred to and literature review was done. Descriptive survey research design adopted. The target population was from the eight water projects being implemented across the country and the accessible population was 1,675 staff members in the eight service boards in the country. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was applied. Questionnaires based on a five-point Likert type scale were distributed through drop and pick-up method for collection of primary data. Reliability of the instrument was measured using Cronbach alpha coefficient and the variable returned satisfactory scores above 0.7. Validity of the study constructs was done through factor analysis and results were significant. One hundred and seventy-four (174) questionnaires were distributed out of which one hundred and forty-four (144) were returned. The descriptive results showed a positive bearing on implementation of water projects, and the same applied to the moderating variable. A regression model was fitted to the data and it was found to be statistically significant. Communication planning explained 36.4% variation in implementation of water projects. There was Strong positive correlation between communication planning and implementation of water projects in Kenya. Concluded that communication planning, had a positive and significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya. Recommended that there should be regular communication between top management and project team members on project matters, for purposes of ensuring that all relevant information was disseminated in a timeous way.

Keywords: Project implementation; Communication planning skills; project size; Communication channels; Stakeholder satisfaction

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In today's dynamic and ever-evolving business environment, project management has become a critical discipline encompassing planning, execution, monitoring, and control of activities led by project managers (Huemann & Turner, 2024). To deliver successful projects on time, within budget, and aligned with stakeholder expectations, project managers and teams must possess a broad range of competencies, including leadership, communication, time management, and problem solving. With the constant emergence of new technologies and methods, staying up to date with recent developments is essential. Effective communication plays a central role in translating project plans into actionable strategies, and where gaps in competencies exist, project organizations must prioritize upskilling efforts (Pieterse et al., 2022). Managing projects requires close oversight to ensure goals set during planning are met, and project managers must execute delivery efficiently to meet stakeholder and client demands. This is especially relevant in water and sanitation projects, which involve not only technical execution but also service delivery, sanitation promotion, and capacity building (Fox & Macleod, 2023; Nel et al., 2023).

In Kenya, Water Service Boards (WSBs) now known as Water Works Development Agencies play a pivotal role in managing national public water works. Their mandate encompasses the development, maintenance, and operation of water infrastructure, alongside the provision of reserve capacity for water services and technical assistance to county governments and other stakeholders (Nyingi et al., 2023). These agencies are also tasked with supporting the Ministry of Water and delivering technical services and capacity building. The scope of their responsibilities reflects a broad institutional role in not only infrastructure development but also the enhancement of local and regional capacity for sustainable water service delivery.

Following sectoral reforms, the provision of water and sanitation services in Kenya has been decentralized to eight regional Water Services Boards, including Athi, Coast, Tana, Lake Victoria North and South, Northern, Rift Valley, and Tanathi. These boards are responsible for investment planning, implementation, and asset management, particularly the development and rehabilitation of water and sewerage facilities (Koros et al., 2023). Though they hold service provision responsibilities, WSBs are not required to deliver services directly; instead, they may delegate this role to public enterprises operating on commercial principles. However, the

licensing system governing their operations has been criticized for being overly bureaucratic and difficult to navigate (Cherotich, 2021), which adds complexity to their vital role in Kenya's water and sanitation service framework.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Today, global investment needs in the water sector exceed \$1.37 trillion, and to meet sustainable development goal six by 2030, investments must increase sixfold from the current level (Javed *et al.*, 2022). Scaling up water investments is meant to result in healthier people and ecosystems, climate-resilient irrigation and drainage services for farmers and improved water storage. As of 2022, 2.2 billion people lacked safely managed drinking water, 3.5 billion lacked access to safely managed sanitation, and 2 billion lacked access to basic hand hygiene facilities. In fiscal year 2023, the World Bank saw increased demand from client countries for assistance in building effective and efficient institutions for delivery of water and sanitation services, and achieving climate-resilient irrigation (Bernards, 2022).

Kenya is a prized destination for international visitors, but it is also a chronically water-scarce country, with a growing population and climate change which are contributing to worsening conditions (Njoki, 2022). The Water Resources Authority (WRA) as a state corporation was established and mandated through delegated authority on behalf of the National government to safeguard the right to clean water by ensuring that there is proper regulation of the management and use of water resources to provide sufficient water for all now and in the future, leading to establishment of Water Service Boards which are located regionally across the country (Lukat *et al.*, 2022).

The water service boards provide policy advice and also support in designing and implementing projects that are sustainable, resilient and inclusive (Malusi, 2023). Despite the concerted efforts to implement various water projects, there have been consistent complaints of projects taking long to complete, being poorly implemented, stalled projects and indeed some becoming outright white elephant projects. A report by World Bank (2023) on Kenya's water projects shows that only 26% of the envisioned water projects have been effectually and proficiently completed, 49% face implementation challenges while the rest have either been abandoned or failed, indicating that there are widespread challenges in implementation of various water projects in the country. In 2021, 2022 and 2023, the abandoned water projects were reported to be at 38%, 44% and 47% respectively (Sakamoto & Kiarie, 2024).

Pieterse *et al.*, (2022) examined critical project management skills for successful delivery of major maintenance projects in the United Kingdom energy sector. Kramskyi *et al.*, (2023) examined the conceptual model for implementation of infrastructure projects in the post-war period in the field of water in Ukraine, thus occasioning a contextual gap. Ngibu (2023) analysed project management skills and performance of youth economic empowerment projects in Kajiado North Sub-County, Kenya; and Rotich and Mungai (2023) reviewed project management technical skills and performance of water, sanitation and hygiene projects in Nairobi City County, Kenya. These studies concentrated on the general aspects of project management skills and performance of water projects, thus occasioning conceptual and methodological gaps. This study focused on the thematic critical project management skill for implementation of water projects and adopted communication planning skill, and moderated by project size, as requisite skill in implementation of water projects in Kenya.

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

1. To determine the influence of communication planning skills on implementation of water projects in Kenya.
2. To investigate the moderating influence of project size on the relationship between communication planning skills and implementation of water projects in Kenya.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Communication planning has no significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya.

H₀₂: Project size has no significant moderating influence on the relationship between Communication planning skills and implementation of water projects in Kenya

2.0 Literature Review

The Communication Accommodation Theory, conceived by Giles (1971), highlights the adjustments individuals make during communication to manage social distance (Kittot & Mberia, 2022). In project management, these adjustments are crucial, as project managers are expected to maintain consistent communication with team members, both face to face and through digital platforms. Effective communication ensures that all team members remain informed about project progress and that the right messages are delivered to the appropriate audiences (Portny & Portny, 2022). Literature shows that project managers spend over 90% of their time communicating, underlining the importance of strong communication skills for both managers and team members. Effective communication helps align everyone with project goals, fosters stakeholder understanding, and increases the likelihood of project success (Ukoha, 2022). Conversely, poor communication often leads to project failure due to the inability to influence key individuals

and external groups (Bernat et al., 2023). As such, project managers must continuously refine their communication strategies, set clear expectations, and ensure consistent information flow across all levels of the project (Elkbuli et al., 2024).

Regular and effective communication improves productivity and promotes teamwork by keeping everyone aligned with project objectives. A well-designed communication plan enables project managers to guide participants toward desired outcomes and ensures that communication flows in all directions, allowing stakeholders to voice concerns and contribute to decision-making (Gaur & Tawalare, 2022; Zwikael et al., 2023). This inclusive communication approach enhances understanding, minimizes errors, fosters collaboration, and helps manage conflict within project teams. To facilitate this, teams rely on various communication tools and techniques tailored to specific projects and environments (Niederman, 2021). These tools include software applications and devices for collecting and distributing project information, while techniques refer to the methods used to communicate effectively within and outside the team. The choice of tools and techniques is influenced by factors such as cost, availability, skill set, and project type (Chigwada & Ngulube, 2023). Communication Accommodation Theory is thus relevant to project management as it underscores the importance of tailored communication planning and demonstrates how effective leadership and communication align to enhance project implementation.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of Communication planning skills on implementation of water projects in Kenya. Communication planning is the independent variable and the moderating variable is project size, while the dependent variable is implementation of water projects. The conceptual framework for this study is indicated in Fig. 2.1

Independent Variables

Moderating Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework (Author, 2025)

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Philosophy

This study adopted a positivist research philosophy. Positivism embraces a philosophical system recognizing only that which can be scientifically verified or which is capable of logical or mathematical proof.

3.2 Research Design

This research adopted descriptive survey research design since the researcher focused attention on objectives formulated, selected a sample, collected data, processed and analyzed the data.

4.0 Findings and Discussion

4.1 General Characteristics of the Study Sample

4.1.1 Response rate

One hundred and seventy-four (174) questionnaires were distributed to respondents out of which one hundred and forty-four (144) questionnaires were duly filled and collected representing 82.7% of the total questionnaires distributed.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Questionnaire Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Returned	144	82.7
Not returned	30	17.3
Total	174	100

The results shown in Table 4.2 demonstrated the high degree of reliability of the questionnaire used in this study.

Table 4.2: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	No. of items	Comments
Communication Planning	.758	7	Accepted
Project Size	.887	7	Accepted
Implementation of Projects	.899	7	Accepted

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

4.2.1 Communication Planning and Implementation of Water Projects

Respondents provided their responses to statements about communication planning and the results are as presented in Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Communication Planning

Statement	SD (%)	D (%)	ND (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	Std Devn.
Project objectives are effectively communicated to team members through organized forums.	0	1.4	25.7	47.9	25	3.97	.752
There is regular communication between top management and project team members on project matters.	0.7	0.7	19.4	49.3	29.9	4.08	.776
Use of automated communication channels has enhanced effective communication in my organization.	2.1	10.4	22.2	41.0	24.3	3.75	1.007
In my organization, project design changes are normally communicated to team members in time to avoid confusion.	0	4.9	23.6	45.8	25.7	3.92	.829
In my organization, reports are prepared and submitted on time to relevant stakeholders.	0.7	6.9	25.7	44.4	22.2	3.81	.887

There is regular feedback on the progress and expectations of the project work.	2.8	6.9	31.2	43.1	16	3.63	.930
There is deliberate follow-up on prior communications by the management to ensure that there is similar interpretation by all members.	0	4.2	31.9	43.1	20.8	3.81	.813

n = 144 *Mean = Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 – 1.8; Disagree (D) = 1.9 – 2.6; Neither Agree nor Disagree (ND) = 2.7 – 3.4; Agree (A) = 3.5 - 4.2; Strongly Agree (SA) = 4.3 – 5.0

Results in Table 4.3 show that majority of respondents and specifically 79.2% agreed that there was regular communication between top management and project team members concerning projects that are underway. The results also indicate that 19.4% of respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement and a paltry 1.4% disagreed with the statement. The statement registered the highest mean score (M = 4.08, SD = .776) and with a standard deviation of less than two, the scores corroborated the great convergence in opinion from respondents about the statement. Results for the second highest mean (M = 3.97, SD = .752) showed that 72.9% of the respondents agreed that project objectives within their institutions were effectively communicated to team members through organized forums and 25.7% neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement and 1.4% of the respondents disagreed.

The results also showed that 71.5% of respondents agreed that in their organizations, project design changes were normally communicated to team members in time to avoid confusion especially during the implementation phase and 23.6% of the respondents were ambivalent about the statement, with 4.9% disagreeing hence posting (M = 3.92, SD = .829). Additionally, 66.6% agreed that in their organizations, reports were prepared and submitted on time to relevant stakeholders for purposes of reading from the same script but 25.7% neither agreed nor disagreed with the position. It was noted that 6.9% disagreed and a small section made of 0.7% of the respondents totally disagreed with the summarized results having (M = 3.81, SD = .887).

Further, on there being deliberate follow-up on prior communications by the management to ensure that there was similar interpretation by all members concerning project goings on elicited 63.9% who agreed with statement with a sizeable 31.9% of the respondents being ambivalent and 4.2% disagreeing (M = 3.81, SD = .813). The study findings also indicate that 65.3% of the respondents agreed that use of automated communication channels had enhanced effective communication in their organizations with 22.2% of the respondents neither agreeing nor disagreeing with the sentiments and 12.5% disagreeing (M = 3.75, SD = 1.007). Further, results indicated that 59.1% agreed that there was regular feedback on the progress and expectations of the project work, and 31.2% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with the position with 9.7% disagreeing (M = 3.63, SD = .930).

This study’s findings agree with Křečková *et al.*, (2020) who reviewed project management communication planning as an improved optimization model with additional recipients and individualized weights, and found that communication plans direct team members in their use of communication channels to understand the trade-offs of different communication plans. The current study similarly agrees with Haupt and Azevedo (2021) who analysed crisis communication planning and non-profit organizations and the analysed resources provided foundational insight for non-profit organizations to proactively develop plans and strategies during non-crisis periods to support their organization when crises occurred. The findings also concur with Setiawan *et al.*, (2021) who reviewed measuring the influence of communication planning towards construction project performance and records that communication planning had been widely adopted and significantly impacted project performances.

The findings similarly concur with Gamil and Abdirahman (2023) who studied the relationship between causes and effects of poor communication in construction projects and the study sought to develop a structural relationship model to study the aforementioned relationship and information exchange in construction projects. The findings were that lack of timely communication among project parties is one of the leading causes of poor communication in the construction industry, and significantly resulted in many negative consequences to construction projects and further has been confirmed that the less rate of communication among parties during the project can cause time and cost overruns.

The results also agree with Lee *et al.*, (2023) who reviewed project coordinators’ perceptions based on organization structure to reduce communication risks in multinational projects and focused on the communication tendencies in different organization structures to facilitate the work of project coordinators and found that by coordinating the communication of project coordinators, the technology and resources of participating project organizations could be timely utilized. The findings also agree with Gichohi *et al.*, (2023) who analyzed project communication and performance of road construction projects in Kenya and found that project communication had a positive and significant relationship with the performance of road construction projects

Table 4.4: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
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Communication Planning	144	2.71	5.00	3.8502	.43282
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Ranked on scale: (Strongly Disagree = 1 – 1.8; Disagree = 1.9 – 2.6; Neither Agree nor Disagree = 2.7 – 3.4; Agree = 3.5 – 4.2; Strongly Agree = 4.3 – 5.0).

Table 4.5: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Communication Planning	.105	144	.001	.987	144	.187

4.2.2 Normal Q-Q Plot of Communication Planning

Departure from normality for communication planning was not so significant and the same was confirmed from the approximation of line of best fit in Figure 4.1. Data was near to normal distribution and could be further used in regression analysis.

Figure 4.1: Normal Q-Q Plot of Communication Planning

4.2.3 Multicollinearity

Table 4.6: Collinearity Coefficients

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Communication Planning	.800	1.250

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects

4.3 Correlation Analysis Results

Table 4.7: Correlation Analysis Results for Study Variables

	Y	X ₁	M
Y	1		
	Pearson Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	144	

X₁	Pearson Correlation	.604**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	144	144	
M	Pearson Correlation	.846**	.117	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.189	
	N	144	144	144

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Key: Y = Implementation of Water Projects; X₁ = Communication Planning; M= Project Size

The results showed that communication planning was strongly and positively related to project implementation (r = 0.604, p = 0.000). These findings illustrate that there is a significant relationship between the dependent variable and independent variable meaning that Communication planning skills have a significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya.

4.3.1 Communication Planning and Implementation of Water Projects

To establish the influence of communication planning (X₁) on implementation of water projects (Y), a regression model was fitted to the data and it was found to be statistically significant (F (1, 142) = 81.453, p = .000). The co-efficient of determination (R²) of .364 was an indicator that communication planning explained 36.4% variation in implementation of water projects. The adjusted R² explained 35.7% variation in implementation of water projects while the remainder could be attributed to other factors not included in the model. The correlation coefficient (R) value of .604 indicated a strong positive correlation between communication planning and implementation of water projects in Kenya.

The hypothesis to be tested was **H₀₁**: Communication planning has no significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya.

The survey results showed that there was a strong positive relationship between communication planning and implementation of water projects in Kenya (β₁= .621, t = 3.152, p-value = .000).

The regression model fitted to test the relationship was;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon;$$

Where;

Y = Implementation of water projects,

β₀ = Constant,

X₁ = Communication planning,

ε = Error term

The null hypothesis stating that communication planning has no significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya (H₀₁: β₁= 0) was therefore rejected (β₁= .621, t = 3.152, p-value = .000) and a conclusion drawn that communication planning (X₁) has a significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya (Y). The resulting regression model was;

$$Y = 3.329 + 0.621X_1$$

The model equation shows that standardized implementation measure of water projects improves by .621 units with one-unit increase in the index of communication planning.

Table 4.8: Regression Analysis Results on Communication Planning and Implementation of Water Projects

a) Model Summary ^b						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.604 ^a	.364	.357	.50409		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication Planning						
b. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects						
b) ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.277	1	13.277	81.453	.000 ^b

Residual	23.199	142	.163
Total	36.476	143	

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication Planning

c) Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.329	.377		8.823	.000
	Communication Planning	.621	.197	.604	3.152	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects

The study results concur with Mardiani (2019) who examined the design of communication planning infrastructure in information technology projects communication management. The study concluded that the recommendations of the communication infrastructure were web-based applications that could be used by project managers in communication planning, such as making project schedules, meeting stakeholders, and sending project progress report schedules.

The subject study concurs with Křečková *et al.*, (2020) who examined project management communication planning with an improved optimization model with additional recipients and individualized weights. The study connected theory and practice to advance a computational model that provided objective-based assessments of communication plans and helped managers to weigh trade-offs of cost, time, and quality in the use of communication channels across the project.

Rotich *et al.*, (2022) examined communication planning and technology integration on implementation of water construction projects in Bomet County, Kenya. The regression results showed that communication planning, positively influenced effective implementation of water projects. The study noted that communication planning influenced implementation of water projects and recommended that the government could embrace the use of technology to equally enhance communication among stakeholders of water projects. The study noted that communication plans defined what information should be communicated, who should receive the information, when that information should be delivered, where communication is to be shared, and how the communications is to be tracked and analysed by relevant stakeholders.

4.3.2 Moderated Multiple Regression Analysis

This study carried out the moderated regression analysis and adopted the following model;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_i M + \epsilon$$

Where;

M = moderating variable (project size)

Table 4.9: Moderated Model Summary

Model Summary ^c				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.604 ^a	.364	.357	.50409
2	.663 ^b	.440	.432	.41574

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication Planning

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication Planning, Project Size

c. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects

In Table 4.9, the findings presented in the model summary show that the value of adjusted R Square was 0.357 prior to introduction of the moderating variable which was project size. When the results are compared to those of model 2 after the introduction of the moderating variable which was project size, the value of adjusted R Square increased to 0.432 which demonstrated that 43.2% variation in implementation of water projects in Kenya could be attributed to changes in moderating communication planning. This means that remainder made up of 56.8% represented other applicable factors that were not included in the obtaining model but which also have a bearing on variation in implementation of water projects.

The study findings show that the moderated variables were significantly and positively related with implementation of water projects in Kenya which was supported by correlation coefficient (R) = 0.663, confirming the strong relationship between the dependent variable and moderated independent variables. From the findings, adjusted R Square increased when the moderating variable which was project size was introduced, increasing from 0.357 to 0.432, which suggested that the introduction of the moderating variable caused an increase in the level of variation in implementation of water projects in Kenya which could actually be explained by the adopted variable of the study.

Table 4.10: Moderated Beta Coefficients

Model		Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error			
		B		Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.139	.572		5.489	.000
	Communication Planning	.337	.110	.317	3.063	.002
2	(Constant)	3.242	.584		5.551	.000
	Communication Planning*M	.367	.106	.357	3.462	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Water Projects

4.3.3 Optimal Model

The following models were fitted based on the overall model before moderation, and the overall moderated model.

$$Y = 3.139 + .337X_1 \dots\dots\dots \text{(Before moderation)}$$

$$Y = 3.242 + .367X_1 * M \dots\dots\dots \text{(Moderated)}$$

The moderated model equation indicates that holding the moderated variables to a constant of zero (communication planning and project size) implementation of water projects in Kenya would still occur at 3.242 units.

The study results show that the interaction of communication planning and project size had a positive influence on implementation of water projects ($\beta_{1M} = 0.367$, p-value = 0.000), demonstrating that the influence was significant since the p-value was less than the chosen significance level of 0.05. Therefore, introduction of the moderating variable project size on communication planning explained 0.367 units of implementation of water projects compared to 0.337 units explained before the variable was moderated, thus indicating that project size had a positive influence on communication planning and implementation of water projects in Kenya.

4.4 Hypotheses Test Results

Table 4.11: Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	β	t	p-value	Decision
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H₀₁: Communication planning has no significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya.	.621	3.152	.000	Reject H ₀₁ since p-value is less than 0.05; (H ₀₁ : $\beta_1 \neq 0$).
H₀₂: Project size has no significant moderating influence on critical project management skills and implementation of water projects in Kenya.	3.242	5.551	.000	Reject H ₀₂ since p-value is less than 0.05; (H ₀₂ : $\beta_2 \neq 0$).

4.5 Summary of Major Findings

The study's objectives were to determine the influence of communication planning on implementation of water projects in Kenya as well as to investigate the moderating influence of project size and implementation of water projects in Kenya. This study established that communication planning had a positive and significant influence on implementation of water projects. The study specifically established that there was regular communication between top management and project team members on project matters, which ensured that all relevant information was disseminated in a timeous way.

The study established that project objectives were effectively communicated to team members through organized forums, to ensure that all forms of communications were done in a systematic manner. Additionally, this study found that in most project organizations, project design changes were normally communicated to team members in time to avoid confusion, thereby having teams that focus on singular objectives and perspectives. However, this study also established that there was no regular feedback on the progress and expectations of the project work, thereby putting in limbo the efforts of project team members to realize effective project implementation.

4.6 Moderating Influence of Project Size

The study investigated the moderating influence of project size on critical project management skills and implementation of water projects in Kenya. The study found that project size had a significant moderating influence on Communication planning skills and implementation of water projects. The study specifically established that project organizations usually sourced for resources from external organizations especially in cases where resource requirements were much more than the project organizations could provide. The study established that project teams in organizations were highly experienced and were continuously trained on nuances of project management, hence inferring that they understood the implementation process of projects. However, it was noted that project organizations did not always undertake projects that were long term for wider outcomes and impact. The findings indicated that project organizations espoused project Communication planning management skills and project size had a bearing on project implementation process at all times

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that communication planning had a positive and significant influence on implementation of water projects in Kenya. Regular communication between top management and project team members on project matters ensured that all relevant information was disseminated in a timeous way. Project objectives were effectively communicated to team members through organized forums to ensure that all forms of communications were done in a systematic manner. Additionally, in most project organizations, project design changes were normally communicated to team members in time to avoid confusion.

The study recommends that there should be regular communication between top management and project team members on project matters for purposes of ensuring that all relevant information was disseminated in a timeous way. The study also recommends that project objectives need to be effectively communicated to team members through organized forums, to ensure that all forms of communications are done in a systematic manner. Additionally, this study recommends that project organizations ought to ensure that project design changes are normally communicated to team members in time to avoid confusion and have teams that focus on singular objectives and perspectives.

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I. Ethical Considerations

Ethical Approval: The study did not use any human subjects or animals hence ethical approval was not needed.

II. Conflict of Interest

There are no potential conflicts of interest present in this study.

III. Data Availability

All references have been provided